

TECHNOLOGY OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: this article provides full information about the technologies and methods of training future teachers for professional activities in family educational organizations.

Key words: child, consciousness, technology, educator, professional activity.

INTRODUCTION

Today, there are many positive changes in the field of preschool education. As the percentage of involvement of young children in preschool educational organizations increases, the demand for qualified specialists also increases. For this reason, the training of qualified specialists in higher education organizations is one of the urgent problems. Future educators should be formed as people who are well-educated in all aspects, and who sincerely love their profession. It is possible to achieve such an achievement as a result of the effectiveness of the technologies of training future teachers for professional activities in higher education organizations.

Education is one of the dearest professions. In turn, the person who is in the place of an educator is responsible for everything: he should be intelligent and educated, he should also be knowledgeable and knowledgeable. The sense of responsibility for the fate of the society and the state of the future generation of each educator determines the description of the title of an educator.

Improvement of the method of developing creative competence of future specialists working in preschool education organizations based on an integrative approach shows the useful and necessary aspects of future specialists in demonstrating their creative and creative abilities in any process.

A pedagogue working in pre-school educational organizations to develop the creative abilities of the growing young generation to fully respond to the demands of the new age, to creatively approach any situation, to understand the world with new views, to form creative thinking and thinking in them, demands creative competence from specialists in their professional activities. The development of the creative competence of the future teachers and specialists of the preschool educational organization, whose role in bringing a perfect person to adulthood, is primarily the responsibility of the pedagogues of the higher educational institution.

According to data (according to youth psychology), children under the age of six have 40% talent potential. Children are very prone to creativity and creativity from the youngest age. Therefore, this period is the right time for children to develop their creative abilities. For this, creative quality and creative competence must be formed in the specialists of the preschool education organization.

An educator performs an important, proud and at the same time responsible task of raising the young generation to become worthy children of our nation. The political maturity of an

educator helps to realize his responsibility to the people and society for raising children, to creatively approach the solution of educational issues, to constantly improve his skills and to support the growth of his colleagues at work. An educator must know the life of the country where he lives, understand the laws of nature and society, and be socially active.

One of the important requirements for an educator is that he must have thoroughly mastered his subject and its methodology. A deep study of the subject and its theory increases the child's interest in science. This raises the reputation of the pedagogue-educator. One of the important qualities and requirements of the teacher's profession is to love children, to be interested in their lives, and to respect each person. Only a person who loves a child and is able to mobilize all his strength and knowledge to raise the child to become a loyal citizen of the great motherland can become a real pedagogue-educator. A person who is indifferent to a child, is not interested in his future, and is indifferent to the education profession cannot be a real pedagogue-educator. The educator provides preschool children with basic knowledge and understanding of nature, social events, and the work of adults, instills in them cultural ethics, the habits of civilized relations with their peers and adults. It educates moral qualities such as kindness, truthfulness, justice, courage, humility, respect for adults, interest in nature, observation, caring for plants and animals, hard work, preserving the results of the work of adults.

The organizational ability of the educator is manifested in organizing the efforts of educators towards the set goal and cooperating with them. Cooperation is a reasonable way to organize work in today's educational environment. The essence of the educator's task of providing information is that the educator is the main source of information for students. The duties of an educator, such as an evaluator, a supervisor and a corrective, are close to each other (in many cases as a whole), coordinating the actions of educators, developing the educational process, inspiring and making certain changes to this process. provides to give.

Educators know from experience that coercion and forced mental work do not lead to success. Instead, it is necessary to develop motivational methods that ensure independent immersion in mental activity when working with educators who have a lot of knowledge.

In the process of preparing future educators for the profession in higher education organizations, it is appropriate to give understanding to future educators in the process of education about the essence of this profession and the requirements and responsibilities imposed on it.

References:

1. Sh. Shodmonova. Preschool pedagogy. T., "Science and technology", 2005.
2. Explanatory dictionary of pedagogy. (Compilers: J. Hasanboyev, H. Torakulov, O. Hasanboyeva, N. Usmanov). T., "Science and technology", 2009.
3. Muslimov N, Usmonboyeva M, Instructional manual for the module "Basics of pedagogical competence and creativity". :- Tashkent 2015, page 120.
4. Rowe A.Dj. Kreativnoe myshlenie / Per.s.angl. V.A. Ostrovkogo. M.: NT Press, 2007,176c.
5. O. A. Holikov. Pedagogical skills. T., "Economy - Finance", 2010.
6. Kharatova Shakhlo "USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS" Science and Education ISSUE 3, March 2022;
7. [hnp://www.detskiysad.ru/ped](http://www.detskiysad.ru/ped).